

Application of Light Water Covariance for Calculation of Nuclear Data Induced Uncertainties

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ABSTRACT

A newly evaluated thermal scattering law (TSL) covariance of light water is used to calculate the nuclear data induced uncertainty in a light-water reactor-like critical benchmark. The new covariance builds off recent theoretical advances in covariance methodologies that incorporate all contributions needed to fully represent the thermal scattering of neutrons off light water. Both stochastic and deterministic methods for data uncertainty propagation are analyzed using the Sampler and TSUNAMI codes, respectively, within the SCALE code suite. The covariance is then transformed into a covariance of the 1D scattering cross section for use in TSUNAMI, and the original full TSL covariance is used to generate random light water TSL samples for use in Sampler. The stochastic analysis incorporates recent changes to Sampler that allow for reaction- and energy-specific perturbations as well as direct perturbations of cross sections. Additionally, the different methodologies analyze the sensitivities of different contributions of the cross sections to the integral data-induced uncertainty. Sampler is used to inspect the effect of both the 1D and 2D contribution of thermal scattering on the data-induced uncertainty, whereas TSUNAMI only investigates the effect of 1D contributions. Similarities and differences between these two approaches are discussed.

Keywords: thermal scattering law (TSL), covariance, light water, nuclear data induced uncertainty

1. INTRODUCTION

Incorporating thermal scattering law (TSL) covariances into neutron transport codes has historically been a challenge for two reasons: a lack of TSL covariances and the inability for transport codes to handle such a covariance. Historically, TSL covariances have been difficult to evaluate and handle for several reasons, ranging from their untenable file sizes to the lack of theoretical understanding on processing and using a covariance of double differential scattering cross sections (DDXSs).

Various efforts over the past few years have worked on methodologies for calculating and evaluating a TSL covariance [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6]. The hope has been that with the inclusion of such data in upcoming nuclear data library releases, the transport codes would implement functionality to include the covariances into their workflows. Before this can be done, however, verification and validation studies are needed to quantify the effect that an existing TSL covariance will have on calculable quantities of interest (e.g., nuclear data induced uncertainties). This is done stochastically by analyzing randomly sampled TSL files from an existing covariance to analyze both the changes in the aggregate mean value as well as standard deviation of calculable quantities.

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A brief theory behind TSLs and TSL covariances is provided in Section 2, details about how this covariance is used to quantify nuclear data induced uncertainties are provided in Section 3, the results and analyses of these calculations are discussed in Section 4, and conclusions and directions for follow-on work are provided in Section 5.

2. THEORY

2.1. Thermal Neutron Scattering

The incoherent inelastic double differential thermal scattering cross section is represented by Eq. (1):

$$\frac{d^2\sigma}{dE_f d\mu} = \frac{\sigma_b}{2k_B T} \sqrt{\frac{E_f}{E_i}} e^{-\beta/2} S(\alpha, \beta), \quad (1)$$

where σ_b is the bound scattering cross section, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the temperature, E_i and E_f are the incident and final energies of the neutron, respectively, and $S(\alpha, \beta)$ is the TSL dependent on two unitless variables α and β , meant to quantify the momentum and energy transfer, respectively. These variables (α and β) are defined by Eq. (2):

$$\alpha = \frac{E_i + E_f - 2\mu\sqrt{E_i E_f}}{A k_B T} \quad \beta = \frac{E_f - E_i}{k_B T}, \quad (2)$$

where μ is the cosine of the scattering angle, and A is mass ratio of the scattering atom to the mass of the neutron.

The TSL $S(\alpha, \beta)$ can be calculated in numerous ways. One such method involves employing the Gaussian approximation:

$$S(\alpha, \beta) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\hat{t} e^{i\beta\hat{t}} e^{-\gamma(\hat{t})}, \quad \gamma(\hat{t}) = \alpha \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\beta P(\beta) [1 - e^{-i\beta\hat{t}}] e^{-\beta/2}, \quad (3)$$

where

$$P(\beta) = \frac{\rho(\beta)}{2\beta \sinh(\beta/2)}, \quad (4)$$

where $\rho(\beta)$ is the phonon density of states. Additionally, for large incident energies, values of α and β may be required that are outside the range of the provided $S(\alpha, \beta)$. In these cases, the short collision time (SCT) approximation is used to analytically calculate $S(\alpha, \beta)$, defined as

$$S(\alpha, \beta, T)_{SCT} = \frac{\exp\left[-\frac{(\alpha - |\beta|)^2 T}{4\alpha T_{eff}(T)} - \frac{|\beta|}{2}\right]}{\sqrt{4\pi\alpha \frac{T_{eff}(T)}{T}}}, \quad (5)$$

where $T_{eff}(T)$ is the effective temperature, defined as

$$T_{eff}(T) = \frac{T}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \beta^2 P(\beta) e^{-\beta/2} d\beta. \quad (6)$$

Therefore, in order to fully define the TSL of a material with incoherent inelastic scattering, only the bound scattering cross section σ_b , the TSL $S(\alpha, \beta)$, and the effective temperature $T_{eff}(T)$ are needed. It is possible to fully describe both the TSL and the effective temperature by the phonon density of states $\rho(\beta)$, thus further reducing the number of degrees of freedom. Quantifying the covariance of phonon density of states on integral systems will not be analyzed in this study; it will be explored more thoroughly in future work.

2.2. TSL Covariance

To calculate the covariance, perturbations were made to a parameterization of the H-H₂O phonon density of states, as described by Maul et al. [4]. The phonon density of states was parameterized into a series of 6 Gaussian functions, each with an associated mean value, standard deviation, and weight. These 18 parameters, along with 6 other parameters describing the two discrete oscillators and free atom scattering cross section, were varied using a multivariate Gaussian distribution with a standard deviation of $\pm 5\%$. This resulted in an ensemble of 4000 random TSL files. These files were then processed using NJOY and fit to a series of DDXS measurements conducted at the SEQUOIA beamline at the Spallation Neutron Source [7] as well as a series of total cross section measurements found in the EXFOR database. The resulting files were then used to calculate a series of 4000 linear weights as calculated using the UMC-B method [8] to calculate the mean value and covariance matrices. The beauty of the UMC-B method is that due to the way the linear weights are calculated, they can be used quantify the mean and covariances of all quantities of interest associated with the fitting procedure (e.g., parameterized phonon density of states, $S(\alpha, \beta)$, DDXS, and total XS).

A resulting covariance matrix of the free atom scattering cross section, $S(\alpha, \beta)$, and effective temperature was generated from the ensemble of linear weights. These three quantities were chosen because they are the inputs required to fully define the TSL of H-H₂O. Although there are other variables that are in the ENDF file that could be perturbed (e.g., number of scattering atoms, atomic mass of hydrogen), these values are either known to such high precision or would break consistency with the isotopic H-1 file and were therefore left unperturbed.

To create the full covariance matrix for H-H₂O, the TSL contribution is inserted into an existing H-1 isotopic covariance (in this work, the ENDF/B-VII.1 H-1 covariance was chosen). The resulting covariance file will therefore contain information about the TSL contribution (below 5 eV) and the isotopic H-1 contribution (above 5 eV). The cross-energy correlations between the two energy regions are taken from the isotopic covariance file; independent testing has shown that this approximation (compared to removing the cross-energy correlations) makes a negligible contribution to integral quantities. A corresponding plot of the covariance of the 1D cross section is shown in Figure 1, and a comparison of the differences in the uncertainty of the scattering cross section between this evaluation, ENDF/B-VII.1, and ENDF/B-VIII.0 is shown in Figure 2.

3. PERTURBATION SCHEME

Neutron transport codes cannot handle a covariance of $S(\alpha, \beta)$; their primary input is covariances of cross sections. As such, a covariance of the DDXS would be the required input for any analysis to be conducted. Unfortunately, although there are several projects currently working in this area, as of the writing of this publication, there is no such implementation in a neutron transport code that can handle a covariance of DDXS. Because of this, a workaround is needed to investigate the effect that this covariance will have on integral systems.

Two complementary SCALE programs were used to test the effect that this covariance would have in calculating nuclear data induced uncertainties: Sampler and TSUNAMI. Each code would be used to calculate the data-induced uncertainties on the LEU-COMP-THERM-042-003 (LCT-042-003) critical benchmark found in the International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP) Hand-

Figure 1. Correlation of H-H₂O cross section.

book [9]. This benchmark was chosen because previous sensitivity studies conducted as part of the VALID test suite [10] showed that it was one of the most sensitive benchmarks to H-H₂O scattering below 5 eV, as shown below in Figure 3. All simulations were performed using a development branch of SCALE [11].

3.1. Sampler Runs

To test the covariance using Sampler, a set of 1000 $S(\alpha, \beta)$ were sampled from the evaluated TSL covariance. These files were then processed using AMPX into an ensemble of 252-group multigroup (MG) libraries. From here, three batches of Sampler runs were conducted:

- A default Sampler run with the ENDF/B-VII.1 library and perturbations.
- A Sampler run where the new evaluated H-H₂O MG file was inserted into the ENDF/B-VII.1 MG library and then perturbed using the SCALE-provided perturbation factors.
- A Sampler run where the ensemble of 1000 H-H₂O files were inserted into the ENDF/B-VII.1 MG library but were left unperturbed while the rest of the library was perturbed.

Comparison of H-1 and H-H₂O MT=2 Uncertainties

Figure 2. Comparison of standard deviations of H-H₂O scattering cross sections.

Sampler relies on the ClarolPlus utility to calculate perturbed cross sections. ClarolPlus applies pre-computed perturbation factors to the cross section of an existing multigroup library to generate perturbed cross sections. These cross sections are re-normalized before ClarolPlus writes a new perturbed multigroup library. This last case (case 3) is unique in that it involves new features recently introduced to the SCALE development branch that allow for reaction- and energy-specific perturbations to be performed by ClarolPlus.

3.2. TSUNAMI Runs

Two covariance files were used in the TSUNAMI calculations. The first is the 252-group covariance based on the ENDF/B-VII.1 library. In this covariance file, the covariances of thermal moderators are assumed to be the covariances of their isotopic constituents in the thermal energy regime (because there is currently no ENDF-provided TSL covariance to use). This means that the current covariance for H-H₂O is the covariance for isotopic H-1. The second covariance used is a 252-group covariance based off of ENDF/B-VII.1 where the contributions from the new evaluated H-H₂O covariance are manually inserted into the existing ENDF/B-VII.1 covariance. This means that the only difference between these two covariance files will be the covariances of H-H₂O below 5 eV; the files are otherwise identical to one another. These covariances were then used alongside an existing sensitivity data file (SDF) of LCT-042-003 to calculate the data-induced uncertainties of the system.

Here, it is worthwhile to demarcate the difference between 1D and 2D cross sections. 1D cross sections describe the probability of interaction at a specific incident neutron energy and are denoted as $\sigma(E_i)$,

Figure 3. Sensitivity profile of H-H₂O scattering cross section for LCT-042-003.

where E_i is the incident neutron energy. 2D cross sections describe the distribution of exit angles and energies at a specific incident energy and are denoted as $\frac{d^2\sigma}{dE_f d\Omega}$, where E_f is the scattered neutron energy, and Ω is the solid angle scattered neutron angle.

4. RESULTS

It should be noted that the comparison of the results between the Sampler runs and TSUNAMI runs is not a true one-to-one comparison. This is because the Sampler runs take the differential scattering contributions into account due to the way that the DDXS files were substituted into the perturbed MG libraries. The TSUNAMI runs, however, only use covariances on the 1D cross section and therefore will not account for changes in the differential (2D) scattering. Results from the Sampler and TSUNAMI runs are shown in Tables I and II, respectively.

Table I. Results from Sampler runs.

H-H ₂ O mean value	H-H ₂ O covariance	k_{eff}	Uncertainty [pcm]
ENDF/B-VII.1	ENDF/B-VII.1	0.99873	608.8
New evaluation	ENDF/B-VII.1	0.99907	608.8
New evaluation	New evaluation	0.99901	628.7

Table II. Results from TSUNAMI runs.

Covariance	%dk/k	total unc. [pcm]
ENDF/B-VII.1	0.6114	610.8
New evaluation	0.6196	618.9

All the differences and similarities in the Sampler simulations are expected results. The k_{eff} between cases 1 and 2 are different because case 2 had the new evaluated H-H₂O cross section data, and the uncertainties are similar because the samples were drawn from the same underlying covariance. Case 3 samples were generated using the new evaluated mean value and covariance, so it is expected that the corresponding mean value k_{eff} results should be very similar to those of case 2. The primary difference comes from the spread of results between case 2 and case 3: a 19.8 pcm difference in the spread of uncertainties corresponding to the different covariances that the samples were drawn from. Similarly, the differences seen in the TSUNAMI runs also show a small difference in the spread of uncertainty (8.1 pcm). Both differences are outside the range of uncertainties of the Monte Carlo runs (5 pcm).

There are two primary takeaways from the results in Tables I and II. The first is that, despite the significant uncertainty showed in Figure 2, the overall impact in data-induced uncertainties is still very small in both the Sampler and TSUNAMI calculations. This is somewhat evident from the sensitivity profile shown in Figure 3 that data-induced uncertainties will not be as pronounced in the low-energy region.

The other finding is that, while the total data-induced uncertainties between Sampler and TSUNAMI are very consistent when considering the ENDF/B-VII.1 covariance (difference of 2 pcm), the same is not true when the new evaluation covariance is used (difference of 9.8 pcm). A difference between the two is expected, as the underlying covariance each calculation is using is different; Sampler uses information from the full 2D covariance while TSUNAMI only uses the 1D covariance. Because the stochastic uncertainty of the SCALE runs is 5 pcm, it is difficult to definitely say if this difference is statistically significant.

5. CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE WORK

A new light water covariance was evaluated and used to determine the nuclear data induced uncertainties of a system sensitive to thermal scattering of light water. Differences between the system with and without a TSL covariance were found to be small, though not negligible. Additionally, differences between Sampler and TSUNAMI calculations were found to be nearly identical without a TSL covariance, and different when a TSL covariance was applied, most likely due to the effect of appropriately quantifying 1D versus 2D scattering sensitivities for this system.

As noted above, there are several open questions that warrant further investigation. A different benchmark with a different sensitivity profile might lead to significantly different results in the differences in the effect of the TSL covariance. Potential candidates include the solution- or MOX- thermal systems available in ICSBEP, as many of these systems tend to have a more pronounced sensitivity profile to light water scattering in the thermal energy region. It would also be interesting to see if covariances of other thermal scattering materials show a similar impact on data-induced uncertainties. Solid moderator materials in heterogeneous systems are of particular interest, as the angular distribution is more likely to play a role in the scattering sensitivity. Programmatically, there are several projects underway to expand the functionality of TSUNAMI to properly account for a DDXS covariance, which would automatically allow for use of a TSL covariance. Other forms of analyses outside of nuclear data induced uncertainties (such as temperature coefficient of reactivity) could also be investigated.

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